

The Late Bronze Age City-State of Ugarit

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Entry tags: Syro-Palestinian Religion, Levantine Religion, Religious Group

Ugaritic religion represents the earliest evidence of widespread "Canaanite" religion. Despite existing under the realm of the Hittite Empire, Ugaritic religion flourished and extant texts help to recreate Levantine religion in the Late Bronze Age.

Date Range: 1500 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: The City-State of Ugarit

Region tags: Syria

The City-State of Ugarit in the Late Bronze Age

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ugaritic Narrative Poetry ed. Simon B. Parker
 - Source 2: Stories from Ancient Canaan ed. Michael D. Coogan and Mark S. Smith
 - Source 3: The City of Ugarit at Tell Ras Shamra by Marguerite Yon
- Notes: Ritual and Cult at Ugarit by Dennis Pardee

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ancient.eu/ugarit/>
- Source 1 Description: Ancient History Encyclopedia
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.livius.org/articles/place/ugarit-ras-shamra/>
- Source 2 Description: Livius

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: There are aspects of the Hittite cult at Ugarit and throughout their vassal states in Syria. In addition, there are elements of Hurrian religion.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: See rituals like RS 1.002 for connections to the political hierarchy. The official cult is tied to the monarchy. See Pardee, *Ritual and Cult at Ugarit* for editions of these texts.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Payment is largely through the sacrificial cult and offerings given to the temples.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: The king is in charge of the cult.

- ↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: See, for example, the primary myths of Ugarit in Coogan and Smith.

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Field doesn't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: See Temples in Yon.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Burial at Ugarit is usually in the domicile but there is a royal cemetery.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: See, "Tombs."

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: See, Yon.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: See, Yon.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: See, Yon.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: See, Yon.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Primarily oriented towards cardinal directions which correlate to natural features.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: There is belief in the netherworld.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The deceased need sustenance in the afterlife which is provided at the burial site.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Netherworld which is presumably like other nearby cultures - bleak for all.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: In the Netherworld which is bounded by mountains.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Usually under the domicile except for the royals.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: There are various types of burial

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: I answer valuable but it may be more intrinsic value for the afterlife. For example, anchors are buried with some deceased (likely sailors) to assist them in the afterlife.

- ↳ Other grave goods:
 - Yes

Are formal burials present:
– Yes

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - No

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - No

- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - Yes

Notes: Most burials are underneath the domestic dwelling.

- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - Yes

Notes: This is the most common type.

- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:
– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes

Notes: El is the supreme god.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes

Notes: See, for example, the interesting text RS 24.258 where El becomes very intoxicated at a feast.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: This is not always explicit but it is implied about he and his consort Asherah.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Kingship is granted by gods but it is not divine kingship.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: El is extremely anthropomorphic. He does things such as lead the divine assembly, but he also drinks heavily and must be taken care of.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a common feature of ANE deities but it does not explicitly appear here.

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
 - Notes: See the Kirta (or Keret) Epic.
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
 - Notes: See the Kirta (or Keret) Epic.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Yes
Notes: El is depicted eating and drinking on multiple occasions.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes
Notes: El is not really a deity of worship so the other deities reflect the majority of worship at Ugarit.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: All human aspects.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Yes
Notes: The dead may have been asked to intercede on behalf of the living but it is unclear.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They are just like the living.
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Yes

- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Especially in regard to treaties, but also more generally.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: These are mainly connected to the sacrificial cult and performance of ritual.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– No

↳ Done randomly:
– Yes
Notes: See Kirita Epic for this.

↳ Other [specify]
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– No
Notes: The afterlife is a bleak place for all.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: This relates to periods where people are not allowed to participate in sexual activity, such as ritual and religious "holidays" or issues of personal "health" (this could relate to things like menstruation so I place "health" in quotations).

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Tied to particular religious and ritual occasions.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily

alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Participation in rituals and religious festivals.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Most families had family gods and also provided offerings to the ancestors.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: For some of these rituals, see Pardee.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Priests as supervisors (presumably using standardized ritual scripts for correct performance).

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: As above, using standardized ritual scripts.

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
 - Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

- No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

- Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
 - No

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
 - No

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
 - Yes

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- A state

Notes: For this period they have local rule but are also a vassal state to the Hittite Empire, overseen by the local Hittite administration at Carchemish.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably, but not definitively.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: The palace would have provided food, but this is likely related to the cult.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably but not definitely.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: It is likely restricted to the elite.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Scribal schools

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: These questions are all "yes" but the religious group and the political groups are not really separable.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The political and religious are always hard to separate, but especially in this case.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Hittite law code is likely present here.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ugaritic alphabetic cuneiform is used for local documents, including religion. Akkadian and Hittite are used for foreign correspondence and other documents. Hurrian is primarily reserved for use as a religious language.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They likely had lands for this but unclear.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know